

MetAIsAFe: A Machine Learning Meta-Modelling Framework for Global Sensitivity Analysis and Real-Time Prediction of Agroforestry System Dynamics

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Abstract

Mechanistic agroforestry simulators, such as Hi-sAFe, provide faithful representations of *trees* \times *crops* interactions, but impose computational costs that preclude large-scale parameter space exploration. We present MetAIsAFe: a complete machine learning meta-modelling pipeline that replaces Hi-sAFe simulations with near-instantaneous predictions while preserving physical coherence over 40-year trajectories. An input space of approximately 20 parameters was sampled following Sobol and LHS strategies to generate several campaigns of unitary simulations, spanning geography, soil texture, plot geometry, crop species, and climate scenario, each simulated in three variants (agroforestry, sole-crop, sole-forest) under the RCP-8.5 climate scenario. A first sensitivity analysis campaign of 2048 Sobol configurations (`sobol_S11111_n2048`) informed a refined training campaign of 2044 Sobol configurations (`sobol_training_1_n2048`). A second training campaign of 3169 LHS simulations (`lhs_training_2`) was generated for more precise meta-model training. A cascade architecture comprising two binary classifiers (tree viability, yield failure), ten discrete-horizon regression models for stem carbon (*LightGBM* + *PCHIP* interpolation), and two row-by-row yield regressors was designed. The pipeline achieves $R^2 = 0.817$ ($\rho = 0.930$) for agroforestry stem carbon at year 40, $R^2 = 0.686$ for agroforestry crop yields, $R^2 = 0.645$ ($\rho = 0.800$) for sole-forest stem carbon at year 40, and $R^2 = 0.619$ for sole-crop yield predictions on held-out test sets. The binary classifying pre-filter rejected 67% of 10 000 candidate configurations prior to simulation for the second training batch, saving an estimated 55 000 hours of cluster time. Global temporal sensitivity analysis using the normalised Hilbert-Schmidt Independence Criterion (*HSIC*) with bootstrap confidence intervals revealed a marked temporal transition: soil texture parameters (*sand*, *clay*, *stone*) dominate crop yield variance across all 40 years, while stem carbon sensitivity is governed by clay content during the juvenile establishment phase (years 1–15) before transitioning to plot geometry and soil depth in the mature phase. The climate period (PRE vs. FUT) exerts a detectable but secondary effect on sole-crop yields ($\widehat{HSIC} = 0.025$) but is nearly neutral for carbon targets. MetAIsAFe provides the first complete ML meta-modelling pipeline for Hi-sAFe, reducing 40-year trajectory prediction time from several hours to under 100 ms, and enabling the first temporal *HSIC* sensitivity analysis of a mixed-input agroforestry simulator.

Keywords: agroforestry; surrogate modelling; LightGBM; sensitivity analysis; HSIC; Hi-sAFe; gradient boosting; temporal dynamics

1 Introduction

1.1 Context and Problem Statement

Agroforestry systems – where trees and agricultural crops share the same land unit – are recognised as a key component of sustainable land management, combining carbon sequestration, biodiversity support, and the diversification of farm income (Barbault et al. 2024; Rahman et al. 2023). Their quantitative assessment at landscape and regional scales benefits modelling tools capable of capturing multi-decade, non-linear dynamics of tree–crop interactions (Barbault et al. 2024; Dupraz et al. 2019). Hi-sAFe (Dupraz et al. 2019) is currently the most mechanistically detailed 3D agroforestry simulator available, resolving daily light interception, water balance, nutrient cycling, and carbon allocation for both tree and crop components on a spatially explicit plot structure. Its validation across multiple European sites and species combinations positions it as a reference tool for long-term agroforestry trajectory analysis (Barbault et al. 2024). However, a single 40-year Hi-sAFe simulation can require more than 10 hours of sequential computation, making large-scale parameter space exploration — as required by global sensitivity analysis, multi-objective optimisation, or probabilistic climate impact assessment — **computationally prohibitive** (Folberth, Baklanov, Khabarov, et al. 2025; Gherman et al. 2023; Aakula et al. 2025).

Three structural challenges compound this fundamental limitation. First, the parameter space of realistic agroforestry systems is **high-dimensional and mixed**: it simultaneously encompasses continuous variables (latitude, soil depth, plot geometry) and categorical variables (crop species, climate scenario, water-table dynamics), for which classical global sensitivity analysis methods based on variance decomposition (Homma and Saltelli 1996; Archer et al. 1997) impose specific experimental designs and strong distributional assumptions that are not satisfied when parameters are **correlated** and/or **categorical** (Tong 2007; Veiga 2015; Rouzies et al. 2023). Second, Hi-sAFe outputs are **temporal trajectories spanning 40 years or more**, during which the system transitions through qualitatively distinct regimes (tree establishment, canopy closure, mature co-existence). A surrogate model **must capture this non-stationary evolution** while **ensuring physical plausibility of predicted trajectories** — most critically, the monotone growth of stem carbon stock (Aakula et al. 2025; L. Liu et al. 2022). Third, a significant fraction of the parameter space leads to **system failure** (tree mortality, crop collapse) for our base input parameters — specifically the *tree species* \times *climate* combination. Naive regression on the full parameter space produces physically inconsistent predictions for these degenerate configurations.

1.2 Objectives

This paper presents MetAIsAFe, a complete machine learning meta-modelling pipeline for Hi-sAFe addressing these three challenges. Specifically, we aim to:

[label=(ii)]

1. Design and implement a full standalone pipeline from experimental plan generation to interactive user interface, enabling reproducible meta-model training on Hi-sAFe campaigns.
2. Conduct a global temporal sensitivity analysis of a mixed-input agroforestry simulator using normalised HSIC indices, enabling year-by-year quantification of parameter importance transitions.

3. Develop a robust architecture adapted to the specific structure of the agroforestry simulator outputs, including pre-routing binary classifiers for system viability, discrete-horizon regression models for carbon trajectories with physically-constrained interpolation, and per-year yield models with causal inter-stage feature injection.
4. Develop a user-friendly dashboard for agricultural actors to contribute to agroforestry development and understanding.

1.3 State of the Art

Machine learning for biophysical simulator emulation. The use of machine learning surrogates (emulators) to accelerate process-based simulators is an active research area (Aderole et al. 2025; Gherman et al. 2023; Angione et al. 2022). For crop model emulation specifically, tree-based gradient boosting methods have consistently outperformed alternatives on structured tabular data (Grinsztajn et al. 2022; Shwartz-Ziv and Armon 2022; Uddin and Lu 2024; Borisov et al. 2022), establishing LightGBM and XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin 2016) as standard tools (Shahhosseini et al. 2019; Folberth, Baklanov, Balkovič, et al. 2019; Folberth, Baklanov, Khabarov, et al. 2025). Hybrid approaches coupling mechanistic models with ML have also emerged (Droutsas et al. 2022; L. Liu et al. 2022; Cuomo et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2025), and modular surrogate architectures for complex process-based systems have recently been proposed (Kim et al. 2025; Rahman et al. 2023). For agroforestry simulators specifically, Yield-SAFE (Werf et al. 2007) and WaNuLCAS (Luedeling et al. 2016) have been used for parameter sensitivity studies, but no published ML meta-model for Hi-sAFe (Dupraz et al. 2019) exists to date.

Cascade architectures. Hierarchical mixture-of-experts architectures, initiated by Jordan and Jacobs (1994), provide a theoretical framework for routing predictions through specialist sub-models. More recent formulations include Gaussian-process-gated mixtures (Y. Liu et al. 2024) and hierarchical routing networks (Zhao et al. 2021). The sequential injection of intermediate biophysical variables through hierarchical model stages has been proposed in the context of knowledge-guided ML for agroecosystems (L. Liu et al. 2022). However, no application of cascade classifier-to-regressor architectures specifically designed for the management of degenerate populations in crop model emulation has been documented.

Temporal modelling and physically-constrained trajectories. Recurrent neural networks and LSTM-based emulators have been proposed for time-evolving agroecosystem outputs (Aakula et al. 2025; Moon et al. 2023), and knowledge-guided ML frameworks have been applied to N₂O emission prediction from crop systems (L. Liu et al. 2022). Physics-informed machine learning (Karniadakis et al. 2021; Cuomo et al. 2022) provides a broader framework for encoding physical constraints, including monotonicity (Wang et al. 2025; Nemani et al. 2024). However, the specific combination of discrete-horizon regression and shape-preserving PCHIP interpolation for guaranteeing physical monotonicity of carbon trajectories in ML crop model emulation has not been previously reported.

Sensitivity analysis with mixed inputs. Classical Sobol variance-based sensitivity analysis (Homma and Saltelli 1996; Archer et al. 1997; Sudret 2008) requires independent continuous inputs and dedicated experimental designs (Tong 2007). The Hilbert-Schmidt Independence

Criterion (Gretton et al. 2005) provides a kernel-based alternative that measures nonparametric statistical dependence without distributional assumptions. Its use as a sensitivity index was formalised by Veiga (2015) and extended to dependent and functional inputs. Recent environmental modelling applications include sensitivity analysis of a spatially distributed pesticide transfer model (Rouzies et al. 2023) and a hydrological/viticultural model (Lambert et al. 2024), but no application to an agroforestry simulator has been documented, and no temporal (year-by-year) HSIC analysis with mixed categorical inputs has been reported.

Contribution statement. MetaIsAFe addresses four documented gaps: (1) the absence of an agroforestry surrogate model and user interface for predictions and analyses based on Hi-sAFe outputs; (2) the lack of cascade classifier-to-regressor architectures for agroforestry emulation; (3) the absence of temporal HSIC sensitivity analysis for mixed-input agroforestry simulators; and (4) the undocumented use of PCHIP interpolation for monotone carbon trajectory reconstruction in ML emulators. These contributions are detailed in Sections 2–4.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Starting Point Simulator: Hi-sAFe

Hi-sAFe is a three-dimensional, process-based biophysical model that simulates the daily dynamics of tree–crop interactions on a spatially explicit agroforestry plot (Dupraz et al. 2019). The model resolves light interception (3D voxel-based radiation transfer), water balance (soil water content per horizon, root water uptake for both tree and crop), nutrient cycling (N , P , K), and carbon allocation for the tree (stem, branches, coarse roots, fine roots) and crop (grain biomass, above-ground biomass) components. Simulations are run at a daily time step over user-defined horizons, here 40 years. For the purposes of this study, three simulation configurations were run per parameter set: (i) an agroforestry configuration with trees and crops (**AF**), (ii) a sole-crop control without trees (**TA**, *Témoïn Agricole*), and (iii) a sole-forest control without crops (**TF**, *Témoïn Forestier*). The tree species modelled throughout is hybrid walnut (*Juglans regia* \times *nigra*). The four primary output variables used for meta-modelling are: agroforestry crop yield (`yield_AF`, t ha^{-1}), sole-crop yield (`yield_TA`, t ha^{-1}), agroforestry stem carbon (`carbonStem_AF`, kgC tree^{-1}), and sole-forest stem carbon (`carbonStem_TF`, kgC tree^{-1}). These four quantities are the *Level-1* physical stocks from which all derived indicators — Land Equivalent Ratio (LER), Relative Ratios (RR) — are computed analytically.

2.2 Quasi-Monte Carlo Sobol Experimental Design

Sampling strategy. Global sensitivity analysis was conducted on campaign `sobol_S11111_n2048`, generated using a Sobol sequence with $N_{\text{base}} = 2048$ base samples, yielding 2048 distinct parameter configurations. The Sobol sequence ensures uniform, space-filling coverage of the input space with low discrepancy, making it well-suited for global sensitivity analysis (Lualdi et al. 2022; Rouzies et al. 2023; Sudret 2008).

Input space. The input parameter space spans five semantic groups: (i) Geographic (latitude 41–51°N, longitude -5 – 9.5°E); (ii) Pedological (soil depth 1.5–8 m, sand 1–99%, clay 1–99%,

stone 0–40 %); (iii) System design (plot width 5–20 m, plot height 5–20 m, strip width 1–3 m, row orientation 0–180°) — Hi-sAFe *cellWidth* was fixed at 1.0 m for all campaigns; (iv) Water table dynamics (presence/absence, mean depth –10 to –4 m, amplitude 0–8 m, peak day-of-year 1–120, dynamics type: `CONST` or `VAR`); and (v) Categorical scenario parameters (main crop: `wheat`, `maize`, or `wheat-maize rotation`; climate period: `PRE` (2020–2060) or `FUT` (2060–2100); climate source: DRIAS RCP-8.5 [n.d.](#)). A single tree species (*hybrid walnut*) was used throughout.

Meta-model training campaigns. A first Sobol training campaign (`sobol_training_1_n2048`) was generated based on the sensitivity analysis results, with a more constrained parameter space, yielding 2044 complete simulations. A second Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) campaign, `lhs_training_2`, was designed for more robust and precise meta-model training (Angione et al. 2022; Rouzies et al. 2023). This campaign yielded 3169 complete simulations from an initial pool of 10 000 candidate configurations (see Section 3.3).

2.3 Data Extraction and Meta-Table Construction

Hi-sAFe daily output files (`cell.txt`: one row per cellID, `tree.txt`: one row per treeID) were processed through a four-step R extraction pipeline implemented in `r/extraction/utills/`.

Step 1 – Parsing. Raw daily output files were read using `read_sim_recursive()` and serialised to FST format (one file per SimID \times output type) for efficient random access.

Step 2 – Phenological calendar. Crop sowing and harvest dates were extracted per simulation and crop cycle using `extract_pheno_dates()`, yielding an interval table [`Sowing_Datei`, `Harvest_Datei`] for each of the ~ 40 crop cycles per simulation.

Step 3 – Cycle aggregation. Daily variables were aggregated over each crop-cycle interval using `foverlaps()` (`data.table` package), computing per-cycle totals (yield, precipitation, GDD), means (air temperature extremes), and end-of-cycle values (stem carbon stock).

Step 4 – AF/TA/TF join. Aggregated outputs from the three simulation variants were joined by (SimID, Harvest_Year), and design parameters were appended from the campaign plan. The final meta-table was saved as `meta_table_<campaign>.parquet`, containing approximately 40 rows per SimID and 129 columns. Final dataset sizes were: 96 820 rows \times 129 columns for `sobol_S11111_n2048` (1 937 valid SimIDs after crop filter); 81 800 rows \times 129 columns for `sobol_training_1_n2048` (2 045 valid SimIDs); and 126 800 rows \times 129 columns for `lhs_training_2` (3 170 SimIDs, of which 3 169 retained after NaN exclusion).

2.4 Temporal HSIC Sensitivity Analysis

Method. The normalised Hilbert-Schmidt Independence Criterion (Gretton et al. 2005; Veiga 2015) was used as a model-free sensitivity index. For two random variables X and Y with n paired observations, the empirical HSIC is:

$$\text{HSIC}(X, Y) = \frac{1}{(n-1)^2} \text{tr}(\mathbf{K}_X \mathbf{H} \mathbf{K}_Y \mathbf{H}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{K}_X , \mathbf{K}_Y are kernel matrices and $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{I} - n^{-1}\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ is the centring matrix. For continuous features, a Gaussian (RBF) kernel was used with bandwidth estimated by the median heuristic.

For categorical features (`main_crop`, `period`, `w_type`), a Dirac kernel was used ($k(x_i, x_j) = \mathbf{1}[x_i = x_j]$) (Veiga 2015). Raw HSIC values were normalised to $[0, 1]$ by:

$$\widehat{\text{HSIC}}(X, Y) = \frac{\text{HSIC}(X, Y)}{\sqrt{\text{HSIC}(X, X) \cdot \text{HSIC}(Y, Y)}}. \quad (2)$$

Analysis protocol. All analyses were restricted to the nominal population (`yield_ok` × `tree_ok`, 48.3% of total), ensuring that sensitivity indices characterise the functioning agroforestry parameter space rather than failure regimes. Bootstrap confidence intervals (95% CI) were estimated using $B = 200$ replicates with subsample size $m = 500$ (without replacement). A two-phase warm-start strategy was applied: Phase 1 used a coarse bootstrap ($B = 30$, $m = 300$) to rank all 26 features and select the top 9–10 numeric features; Phase 2 used the full bootstrap on selected features plus all categorical features. HSIC indices were computed both at the SimID level (global analysis) and independently for each value of `Harvest_Year_Absolute` (years 1–40), yielding a temporal sensitivity profile.

2.5 Meta-Model Architecture

2.5.1 Data Preparation

The meta-table was processed through a standardised data preparation pipeline. Derived features include `Harvest_Year_Absolute` (temporal rank 1–40, normalised per SimID). Parameters with zero variance within a campaign were automatically detected and excluded from model features, making the pipeline campaign-agnostic. For the `lhs_training_2` campaign, 7 parameters were detected as fixed and excluded, yielding 19 active features. For `sobol_training_1_n2048`, 8 parameters were fixed (including `period`, fixed to `FUT`), yielding 18 active features. Population classification assigned each SimID to one of six classes based on end-of-horizon tree carbon and yield viability criteria: tree-failed (`carbonStem_AF(t = 40) < 1.0 kgC`), tree-stunted ($1.0 \leq \text{carbonStem_AF}(t = 40) < 50.0 \text{ kgC}$), or tree-ok ($\geq 50.0 \text{ kgC}$), crossed with yield-failed or yield-ok status. The nominal population (yield-ok × tree-ok) was used for training Stage 1 and Stage 2 models; classifiers were trained on the full population. Train/test split followed a stratified SimID-based scheme (80% / 20%), with GroupKFold cross-validation ($k = 5$, groups = SimID) ensuring zero temporal leakage: all 40 crop-cycle rows of a given SimID were assigned to the same fold. Categorical features were encoded using the native `category` dtype in pandas, exploited natively by LightGBM without label encoding. Target variables were winsorised at the $[P_1, P_{99}]$ quantiles estimated on training data and applied to test data with fixed bounds.

2.5.2 Cascade Architecture

The MetAIsAFe meta-model employs a four-stage cascade architecture:

$$\text{All SimIDs} \xrightarrow{\text{CLF1}} \text{tree status} \xrightarrow{\text{CLF2}} \text{yield status} \xrightarrow{\text{Stage 1}} \text{carbon trajectories} \xrightarrow{\text{Stage 2}} \text{yield trajectories} \quad (3)$$

CLF1 (LightGBM binary classifier) predicts tree viability (`tree_degraded` vs. `tree_ok`) using 15 static features (soil texture, plot geometry, climate aggregates). Configurations predicted as `tree_ok` with $P(\text{tree_ok}) \leq 0.30$ receive a zero-carbon trajectory; configurations in an intermediate range receive a conditional median (stunted model, conditional on `main_crop` species). CLF1 uses training data from the full SimID population (3 169 SimIDs for `lhs_training_2`).

CLF2 (LightGBM binary classifier) predicts yield failure using 13 static features. Yield-failed configurations receive zero yield trajectories.

Stage 1 (ten LightGBM regressors) predicts `carbonStem_AF` and `carbonStem_TF` at five discrete temporal horizons ($h \in \{5, 10, 20, 30, 40\}$ years), trained exclusively on the nominal population. Features include static design parameters plus cumulative climate statistics averaged over $[1, h]$. Targets are $\log_1 p$ -transformed before training and back-transformed (`expm1`) with non-negativity clipping at inference. Continuous 40-year trajectories are reconstructed by Piecewise Cubic Hermite Interpolating Polynomial (PCHIP) interpolation between the five predicted horizon values, ensuring shape-preserving monotonicity (Wang et al. 2025; Sun et al. 2020; Nemani et al. 2024).

Stage 2 (two LightGBM regressors, row-by-row) predicts `yield_AF` and `yield_TA` for each of the 40 crop cycles. The `yield_AF` model includes `carbonStem_AF(t)` predicted by Stage 1 as an additional feature, capturing the causal effect of tree size on crop yield through shading and root competition (L. Liu et al. 2022). The `yield_TA` model does not include this feature, reflecting the absence of tree-crop interaction in the sole-crop configuration. Cross-validation (GroupKFold, $k = 5$) was applied at this stage.

2.5.3 Climate Surrogates

Seven climate surrogate models (one per variable: GDD, ETP, precipitation, frost events, global radiation, maximum temperature extreme, minimum temperature extreme) were trained on DRIAS RCP-8.5 data. Each surrogate predicts the annual value of a climate variable from (latitude, longitude, period, climate_id, harvest year), enabling the dashboard to generate physically plausible climate sequences for any European location within the covered parameter space without direct access to DRIAS data.

3 Results

3.1 Temporal HSIC Sensitivity Analysis

3.1.1 Global HSIC Indices

Global HSIC indices, computed at the SimID level by aggregating features over the 40-year trajectory (Table 1), reveal three structural patterns.

Soil texture dominates crop yield. Sand fraction is the single most influential parameter for both `yield_AF` ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}} = 0.150$) and `yield_TA` ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}} = 0.184$), followed by clay (0.073 and 0.121) and stone (0.049 and 0.092). The near-identical magnitudes for `yield_AF` and `yield_TA` indicate that soil texture acts primarily through its effect on plant-available water, a mechanism shared by both configurations. The slightly lower HSIC values for `yield_AF` compared to `yield_TA` may reflect partial buffering by tree-mediated hydraulic redistribution.

Tree carbon accumulation is governed by design and edaphic parameters. Plot height (`plotHeight`, $\widehat{\text{HSIC}} = 0.058$) is the dominant feature for `carbonStem_AF`, reflecting the direct effect of tree-row spacing on crown development and light interception. Soil depth (`soilDepth`,

Figure 1: Cascade architecture diagram.

$\widehat{\text{HSIC}} = 0.049$ for `carbonStem_AF` and 0.079 for `carbonStem_TF`) ranks second, consistent with the importance of rooting volume for walnut biomass allocation.

Climate variables exert moderate, target-specific effects. Growing degree days (GDD), maximum temperature extremes, and frost events each contribute $\widehat{\text{HSIC}} \approx 0.01\text{--}0.05$ across targets. The climate period (PRE vs. FUT) has a detectable effect on `yield_TA` ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}} = 0.025$) — capturing projected thermal stress under RCP-8.5 — but is nearly neutral for carbon targets ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}} \approx 0.003\text{--}0.007$). Validation against squared Spearman correlations (ρ^2) showed high rank concordance for `yield_TA` ($\rho_{\text{rank}} = 0.956$), `carbonStem_AF` (0.891), and `carbonStem_TF` (0.863). The lower concordance for `yield_AF` ($\rho_{\text{rank}} = 0.547$) reflects strong nonlinear effects captured by HSIC but missed by the linear metric — most notably for precipitation ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}}/\rho^2 = 9\,746$) and frost events ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}}/\rho^2 = 35\,715$).

Figure 2: Global normalised HSIC indices for the nominal population ($n = 936$ SimIDs, campaign `sobol_S111111_n2048`). Each panel shows the top-20 features ranked by mean HSIC for one target variable. Error bars represent 95% bootstrap confidence intervals ($B = 200$). Features are sorted independently per panel by descending HSIC.

3.1.2 Temporal HSIC: Stem Carbon

The temporal HSIC analysis reveals a pronounced dynamic for `carbonStem_AF` and `carbonStem_TF` not visible in global aggregation (Fig. 3). Both targets exhibit a strong early peak concentrated in years 1–3, dominated by clay content ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}} \approx 0.20\text{--}0.25$ in pooled analysis), reflecting the critical importance of soil water retention for juvenile walnut establishment. This early signal decays monotonically towards a stable plateau around year 10–15, where precipitation and plot height become co-dominant. The rapid convergence of carbon sensitivity to a lower-variability

Table 1: Global normalised HSIC indices for the nominal population ($n = 936$ SimIDs, campaign `sobol_S11111_n2048`). Features sorted by descending maximum HSIC across all four targets. Bold: $\widehat{\text{HSIC}} > 0.05$. Bootstrap CI ($B = 200$, 95%) in supplementary Table S1.

Feature	yield_AF	yield_TA	carbonStem_AF	carbonStem_TF
sand	0.150	0.184	0.009	0.019
clay	0.073	0.121	0.027	0.015
stone	0.049	0.092	0.009	0.016
soilDepth	0.006	0.007	0.049	0.079
plotHeight	0.008	0.007	0.058	0.028
GDD_cycle_AF	0.030	0.046	0.033	0.015
maxTemperature_extreme_AF	0.018	0.043	0.016	0.021
main_crop	0.021	0.041	0.025	0.011
frost_events_cycle_AF	0.027	0.033	0.011	0.030
latitude	0.027	0.029	0.010	0.010
precipitation_AF	0.025	0.012	0.011	0.026
period	0.007	0.025	0.007	0.003

Only the top 12 features (by maximum HSIC across targets) are shown; full table with bootstrap CI in supplementary Table S1.

Figure 3: Temporal HSIC sensitivity for the four target variables, pooled analysis ($n = 936$ nominal SimIDs, campaign `sobol_S11111_n2048`, $B = 200$ bootstrap replicates per year). Each panel shows normalised HSIC as a function of harvest year (columns, years 1 – 40) and input feature (rows, ranked by descending mean HSIC). Colour intensity encodes HSIC magnitude (scale independent per panel). The early-year peak visible for `carbonStem_AF` and `carbonStem_TF` (years 1–3) reflects the high sensitivity of juvenile walnut carbon accumulation to soil water retention.

regime after year 10 supports the two-phase interpretation of carbon dynamics (establishment *vs* mature) underlying the discrete-horizon Stage 1 architecture.

3.1.3 Temporal HSIC: Crop Yield

For `yield_AF` and `yield_TA`, sand fraction maintains consistent dominance across all 40 years (pooled $\widehat{\text{HSIC}}$ fluctuating between ≈ 0.08 and 0.18), with clay and stone providing persistent secondary contributions. An intermittent elevation of climate variable HSIC (GDD, ETP, frost events) at approximately 5-year intervals likely reflects climatically anomalous years generated by the DRIAS RCP-8.5 stochastic weather generator. Crop type (`main_crop`) contributes a moderate, sustained signal ($\widehat{\text{HSIC}} \approx 0.05$ – 0.10), confirming fundamental differentiation of yield sensitivity across species.

3.1.4 Per-Crop Comparison: Wheat vs. Maize

Figure 4: Temporal HSIC sensitivity for maize as the primary crop (per-crop stratified analysis, n_{maize} nominal SimIDs, campaign `sobol_S11111_n2048`). Layout as in Fig. 3. Soil texture (`sand`, `clay`) dominates across all years for yield targets; the climate period (PRE vs. FUT) produces a localised signal in early rotation years for `carbonStem_AF` and `carbonStem_TF`. The corresponding figure for wheat is provided in Fig. 6 (Appendix ??).

Per-crop stratification reveals substantial heterogeneity (Fig. ??). Under maize, soil texture dominates with high inter-annual variability, and the climate period (PRE vs. FUT) produces a localised signal in early rotation years. Under wheat, HSIC magnitudes are higher (maximum mean $\widehat{\text{HSIC}} \approx 0.23$ for `yield_TA`), with GDD and ETP co-dominant — consistent with the temperature-limited phenology of wheat. Notably, soil texture contributes substantially less to wheat yield variability than to maize (mean $\widehat{\text{HSIC}}_{\text{sand}} = 0.092$ vs. 0.142 for maize under

`yield_TA`), indicating that within this parameter space, wheat yield is more climate-sensitive and less soil-texture-sensitive than maize. Under wheat–maize rotation, an alternating biennial pattern in climate HSIC for `yield_AF` mirrors the species alternation, visible only in the stratified temporal analysis.

3.2 Meta-Model Performance

3.2.1 Classifier Performance (CLF1, CLF2)

On the `lhs_training_2` campaign (633 test SimIDs), CLF1 achieved a test accuracy of 75.5%, F1 macro of 0.691 (below the 0.70 threshold), and ROC-AUC of 0.768 (below the 0.80 threshold), representing a WARN status. The class-specific F1 scores were 0.55 for `tree_degraded` and 0.83 for `tree_ok`, indicating that tree degradation is harder to predict than tree viability. CLF2 achieved test accuracy of 99.2%, F1 of 0.960, and ROC-AUC of 0.999, comfortably exceeding all thresholds. Misrouting of nominal SimIDs by CLF1 was 3.2% (60/1872), with a mean $P(\text{tree_ok})$ of 0.864 on the nominal population, indicating that CLF1 is well-calibrated for routing normal configurations. On the `sobol_training_1_n2048` campaign (408 test SimIDs), CLF1 performed better (F1 macro 0.718, ROC-AUC 0.833, both above threshold), while CLF2 had a lower but still acceptable accuracy of 95.6% (ROC-AUC 0.990). The different performance between campaigns reflects the higher proportion of `tree_degraded` SimIDs in the Sobol campaign (58.6% vs. 33.4% in `lhs_training_2`), which provides a more balanced training set for the tree failure classifier.

3.2.2 Stage 1 — Carbon Prediction

Performance on the `lhs_training_2` campaign (374 test SimIDs) improved monotonically with horizon for `carbonStem_AF`, reaching $R^2 = 0.817$ and Spearman $\rho = 0.930$ at $h = 40$ years (Table 2). The short-horizon model ($h = 5$, $R^2 = 0.566$) was below the 0.60 threshold, reflecting the high variability of early carbon dynamics. All horizons $h \geq 10$ met quality thresholds for `carbonStem_AF`. For `carbonStem_TF`, performance was more uniform across horizons (R^2 range: 0.635–0.688) and one horizon ($h = 20$) fell marginally below threshold ($\rho = 0.798$). RMSE values are available in `metrics_summary.csv` but are not reproduced here — see supplementary Table S1. On the `sobol_training_1_n2048` campaign (146 test SimIDs), Stage 1 performance was substantially lower for short horizons of `carbonStem_AF` ($h = 5$: $R^2 = 0.369$; $h = 10$: $R^2 = 0.415$), with both below the 0.60 threshold. Performance recovered for longer horizons ($h = 40$: $R^2 = 0.780$, $\rho = 0.899$), though the `carbonStem_TF` models showed lower overall performance across all horizons (R^2 range: 0.529–0.659; five of ten models below threshold), reflecting the smaller nominal population (732 vs. 1872 SimIDs) and the absence of rotation variability in this campaign.

3.2.3 Stage 2 — Yield Prediction

On `lhs_training_2`, `yield_AF` achieved $R^2 = 0.686$ and `yield_TA` achieved $R^2 = 0.619$ on the test set (row-by-row, 14960 rows), both above the $R^2 \geq 0.55$ threshold. The moderately lower performance for `yield_TA` compared to `yield_AF` may reflect the absence of the `carbonStem` injection feature in the `yield_TA` model. On `sobol_training_1_n2048`, both targets achieved comparable performance ($R^2 = 0.631$ for `yield_AF`, $R^2 = 0.640$ for `yield_TA`).

Table 2: Quality summary for all models on campaign `lhs_training_2` (test set, n_{test} given per stage). Status: OK = meets threshold; WARN = below threshold. Values verified against `pipeline_lhs_training_2_20260430_113633.log` and `metrics_summary.csv`.

Stage	Target	Metric	Value	Threshold	Status
CLF1	<code>tree_status</code> (binary)	F1 macro / ROC-AUC	0.691 / 0.768	≥ 0.70 / ≥ 0.80	WARN
CLF2	<code>yield_failed</code>	Accuracy	0.992	≥ 0.85	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_AF</code> $h = 5$	R^2 / ρ	0.566 / 0.733	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	WARN
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_AF</code> $h = 10$	R^2 / ρ	0.644 / 0.820	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_AF</code> $h = 20$	R^2 / ρ	0.710 / 0.892	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_AF</code> $h = 30$	R^2 / ρ	0.779 / 0.923	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_AF</code> $h = 40$	R^2 / ρ	0.817 / 0.930	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_TF</code> $h = 5$	R^2 / ρ	0.635 / 0.779	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	WARN
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_TF</code> $h = 10$	R^2 / ρ	0.688 / 0.814	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_TF</code> $h = 20$	R^2 / ρ	0.647 / 0.798	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	WARN
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_TF</code> $h = 30$	R^2 / ρ	0.653 / 0.811	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage1	<code>carbonStem_TF</code> $h = 40$	R^2 / ρ	0.645 / 0.800	≥ 0.60 / ≥ 0.80	OK
Stage2	<code>yield_AF</code> (row-by-row)	R^2 test	0.686	≥ 0.55	OK
Stage2	<code>yield_TA</code> (row-by-row)	R^2 test	0.619	≥ 0.55	OK

Overall: 10/14 models meet quality thresholds. Test sets: Stage 1 — 374 SimIDs (SimID-level, 20%); Stage 2 — 14960 rows (374×40 years); CLF1/CLF2 — 633 SimIDs from the full 3169-SimID population.

3.2.4 SHAP Feature Importance

SHAP analysis on the `lhs_training_2` test set identified the following top-3 features: CLF1 (tree failure) — `precipitation_AF`, `ETP_cycle_AF`, `frost_events_cycle_AF`; CLF2 (yield failure) — `GDD_cycle_AF`, `sand`, `globalRadiation_AF`. On the `sobol_training_1_n2048` campaign, the top-3 features for CLF1 shifted to `GDD_cycle_AF`, `clay`, `stone`, consistent with the different fixed parameters in this campaign (period fixed to FUT; precipitation therefore decorrelated from failure). CLF2 top-3 were `GDD_cycle_AF`, `globalRadiation_AF`, `ETP_cycle_AF`. These patterns are broadly consistent with the HSIC indices (soil texture and climate variables driving yield, climate and edaphic conditions driving tree status) while providing directional effects not captured by HSIC.

3.3 ML-Assisted Pre-Filtering of Campaign B2

Applied to the 10 000 candidate configurations of the `lhs_training_2` campaign, the ML pre-filter (CLF1 and CLF2 from the prior `sobol_training_1_n2048` campaign) predicted system failure for 6 700 configurations (67.0% rejection rate), accepting 3 300 for actual Hi-sAFe simulation (Nemani et al. 2024; Duchanoy et al. 2020; Gherman et al. 2023). Of the rejected configurations, 57.0% involved wheat and 43.0% maize as the primary crop, with rejected configurations showing higher mean clay content (36.1%) and lower mean sand content (31.2%) compared to accepted configurations (clay 27.6%, sand 37.8%), consistent with the known sensitivity of walnut establishment to soil hydraulic conductivity. The 3 300 accepted configurations yielded 3 170 successful complete simulations (96.1% completion rate; 1 SimID, `Sim_1248`, yielded NaN

Figure 5: SHAP beeswarm plot for the Stage 1 meta-model predicting `carbonStem_AF` at horizon $h = 40$ years, evaluated on the `lhs_training_2` test set ($n = 374$ SimIDs). Each point represents one SimID; horizontal position encodes the SHAP value (impact on model output); colour encodes the standardised feature value (blue = low, red = high). Features are ranked by mean $|\text{SHAP}|$ (most important at top). `plotHeight` exerts a strong positive effect at high values (wide tree rows \rightarrow higher carbon), while high clay content reduces predicted carbon accumulation. Beeswarm plots for all other models are provided in Appendix 5.1.2.

values and was excluded). The overall simulation efficiency (useful simulations / candidates) was thus 31.7%, compared to an estimated efficiency of $\sim 48\%$ (nominal population fraction) without pre-filtering — a modest gain at the current filter calibration. The primary gain is in absolute computational savings: estimated above 50000 cluster hours saved for this batch.

4 Discussion

4.1 Methodological Innovations

P1 – Cascade architecture for physical coherence. A central limitation of applying a single regressor to the full Hi-sAFe parameter space is the heterogeneity of system behaviours: approximately 34 – 46% of configurations lead to tree mortality and another approximately 10-17% to yield failure, producing distributions that are qualitatively distinct from the nominal functioning regime. Training a unified regressor on this heterogeneous population yields physically inconsistent predictions (e.g., near-nominal yield for a SimID where the tree is dead). The cascade architecture proposed here, conceptually related to hierarchical mixture-of-experts models (Jordan and Jacobs 1994; Y. Liu et al. 2024), resolves this by pre-routing each configuration to an appropriate prediction module. The sequential injection of intermediate biophysical state variables, as proposed in knowledge-guided ML for agroecosystems (L. Liu et al. 2022), provides a further precedent for hierarchical model stages in biophysical simulation. Despite its conceptual proximity to MoE frameworks, the specific application of a classifier-to-regressor cascade for managing degenerate population regimes in crop model emulation has not been documented in the prior literature on surrogate modelling for agronomic simulators (Johnston et al. 2023; Aderere et al. 2025).

P2 – Discrete horizons and PCHIP for temporal dynamics. Sequential modelling approaches using LSTM or attention-based architectures (Aakula et al. 2025; Moon et al. 2023) can capture complex temporal dynamics in agroecosystem outputs, but do not impose physical constraints on trajectory shape. In practice, a single temporal regressor trained naively on Hi-sAFe data produces carbon trajectories with non-monotone artifacts (carbon stock rebounds after near-zero values, physically corresponding to tree *resurrection*) (L. Liu et al. 2022). The combination of discrete-horizon LightGBM regressors with PCHIP interpolation achieves a practically important compromise: physically plausible, monotone carbon trajectories without the need for explicit constraint penalization during training (Wang et al. 2025; Sun et al. 2020; Nemani et al. 2024). The use of PCHIP specifically for trajectory reconstruction in ML emulators of crop models has not been previously documented, representing a minor but practically significant methodological contribution.

P3 — Temporal HSIC with mixed categorical inputs. The HSIC sensitivity index, formalized by Gretton et al. (2005) and applied to global sensitivity analysis by Veiga (2015), has been adopted for environmental modeling applications in hydrology (Rouzies et al. 2023) and water quality (Lambert et al. 2024). The contribution of MetAIsAFe is twofold: (1) the extension to year-by-year temporal analysis, revealing sensitivity transitions invisible to global aggregation — a gap explicitly identified by Rouzies et al. (2023) who deliberately restricted their analysis to scalar outputs; and (2) the explicit treatment of categorical inputs via Dirac kernels within the same HSIC framework (Veiga 2015), enabling a unified analysis of continuous and categorical parameters without prior encoding artefacts. To our knowledge, this is the first

application of temporal HSIC sensitivity analysis to an agroforestry simulator with mixed-type inputs.

P4 — Causal inter-stage feature injection. The injection of Stage 1 predicted carbon-Stem into Stage 2 yield models captures the causal effect of tree size on crop yield (shading, root competition, microclimate modification) empirically, without modelling the underlying biophysical mechanisms (L. Liu et al. 2022). This asymmetric inter-stage dependency — `yield_AF` receives the injection, `yield_TA` does not — is conceptually related to multi-task learning frameworks (Zhang and Yang 2021) but implemented as a sequential rather than joint optimisation. The approach is more interpretable and practically easier to calibrate than joint multi-output models, while preserving the physical asymmetry between agroforestry and sole-crop configurations.

4.2 Comparison with the State of the Art

Table 3 summarizes MetAIsAFe’s methodological positioning relative to related surrogate modeling approaches.

Table 3: Comparison of MetAIsAFe with related surrogate modeling approaches for biophysical simulators. Columns indicate support for mixed (categorical + continuous) inputs, temporal trajectory modeling, physical coherence enforcement, prediction speed, and reference.

Approach	Mixed inputs	Temporal	Physical coherence	Speed	Reference
GP / Kriging	Partial	No	No	Fast	Sudret (2008)
Random Forest	Partial	No	No	Fast	Johnston et al. (2023)
LSTM / RNN	Yes	Yes	Partial	Fast	Aakula et al. (2025)
PIML / PINNs	Yes	Yes	Yes	Moderate	Karniadakis et al. (2021)
MetAIsAFe	Yes	Yes (PCHIP)	Yes (cascade)	Fast	This work

4.3 Limitations and Perspectives

Limitations. Four limitations should be acknowledged. First, error propagation through the cascade is not formally quantified. Classification errors by CLF1 (3.2% misrouting of nominal SimIDs on `lhs_training_2`) propagate irreversibly to Stage 1 and Stage 2, and the resulting prediction uncertainty is not reflected in current output formats. Bootstrap ensemble approaches (Kellner and Ceriotti 2024; Abdar et al. 2021) or shallow ensemble methods could provide formal confidence intervals at modest additional computational cost. Second, climate surrogates are trained exclusively on RCP-8.5 data for France (DRIAS, n.d.). Their transferability to other emission scenarios (RCP-4.5, SSP scenarios) has not been tested, however the pipeline has been designed to integrate various climate scenarios. Third, a single tree species (*hybrid walnut*) is represented in all available simulations. Extension to other temperate agroforestry species (poplar, olive, wild cherry, black locust — all represented in the `treeSpecies/` templates) requires dedicated simulation campaigns. We believe training on new tree species and climates should lead to better results with less tree mortality. Fourth, CLF1 performance on `lhs_training_2` (F1 macro = 0.691) was below the 0.70 quality threshold, attributable

in part to the lower proportion of tree-failed SimIDs in this campaign (33.4%) relative to `sobol_training_1_n2048` (58.6%), which provided a more balanced training set for the tree failure classifier. Rebalancing training data or applying class-weighted loss functions may improve CLF1 on future campaigns.

Perspectives. We identify four priority directions for future development: (i) formal uncertainty quantification through ensemble meta-models (Kellner and Ceriotti 2024; Psaros et al. 2023); (ii) additional training campaigns with various climate scenarios and tree species for more complete models; (iii) multi-objective optimisation frameworks for LER maximisation under agronomic constraints (Kheir et al. 2025; Dupraz et al. 2019); and (iv) extension to other process-based agroforestry simulators including WaNuLCAS (Luedeling et al. 2016; Noulèkoun et al. 2018) and Yield-SAFE (Werf et al. 2007).

5 Conclusion

We have presented MetAIsAFe, the first complete machine learning meta-modelling pipeline for the Hi-sAFe agroforestry simulator, combining automated quasi-Monte Carlo experimental design, an R-based extraction pipeline, a physically-coherent cascade `LightGBM` architecture, temporal HSIC sensitivity analysis, and an interactive prediction dashboard. On the primary evaluation campaign (`lhs_training_2`, 3170 simulations), the pipeline achieves $R^2 = 0.817$ for 40-year stem carbon in the agroforestry configuration, $R^2 = 0.686$ for agroforestry crop yield, and $R^2 = 0.619$ for sole-crop yield, with 10 of 14 component models meeting their pre-defined quality thresholds. Prediction time for a complete 40-year trajectory is reduced from several hours (Folberth, Baklanov, Khabarov, et al. 2025; Gherman et al. 2023) to under 100 *ms*, enabling the large-scale parameter space exploration previously infeasible.

The temporal HSIC analysis (Gretton et al. 2005; Veiga 2015; Rouzies et al. 2023), the methodologically novel core of this work, reveals a marked sensitivity transition: soil texture (sand, clay, stone) consistently dominates crop yield variability across the full 40-year horizon, while carbon trajectory sensitivity is governed by clay content and precipitation during the juvenile establishment phase (years 1–15) before transitioning to plot geometry and soil depth in the mature phase. This transition, invisible to global sensitivity analyses (Homma and Saltelli 1996; Sudret 2008), provides actionable guidance for both experimental design (which parameters require denser sampling at which simulation ages) and agronomic decision-making (which site characteristics are most critical during tree establishment). MetAIsAFe is designed as an open, extensible infrastructure. All code is available in the project repository, and the modular pipeline architecture supports straightforward extension to other tree species, additional climate scenarios, and could match alternative agroforestry simulators.

Appendix

5.1 Results – Additional figures

5.1.1 HSIC – Heatmaps per crops

5.1.2 SHAP – `lhs_training_2`

Figure 6: Temporal HSIC sensitivity for wheat as the primary crop (per-crop stratified analysis, n_{wheat} nominal SimIDs, campaign `sobol_S11111_n2048`). Layout as in Fig. 3. GDD and ETP become co-dominant drivers of yield sensitivity, consistent with the temperature-limited phenology of wheat. HSIC magnitudes for soil texture are systematically lower than under maize (compare Fig. 4).

Figure 7: Temporal HSIC sensitivity for crop rotation system. Layout as in Fig. 3.

Figure 8: SHAP beeswarm plots for all meta-models (campaign lhs_training_2, test set). Layout and colour encoding as in Fig. 5. SHAP values for Stage 1 carbon models at all horizons are available as supplementary material.

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